

>>Fibonacci Pressure waned; Feb 3rd prediction from 2/1/22 AIM call “on the money”

In this letter:

- Small update from publishing on MIMS 2.1.212c
- New concept, “volumocity”

MIMS 2.1.212d - Pressure Reversal Achieved

Paper c predicted February. Exact analysis predicted the 3rd. The 4th had drastic expansion and “gapping”

February 2022

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
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Re: “How did you AIMsters predict the reversal?” & “How long will it expand?”

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

Looking at the Thinkorswim minimap, we see where the entire study started, and how we’ve followed the changes, with fibonacci and channel studies, all the way through the complete dispersal of the downward pressure, and release into rapid expansion.

So what can this analysis tell us about the future? Both since cryptocurrency is a MIMS, and this study is a MIMS, and the entire purpose of the philosophy - as originally proposed - is futurization. I recommend people review the futurization video/interview with mathematician Buddy Dougherty (creator of the Dougherty Set), available on the Pulse show on Youtube.¹

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jTQ2uvDtgak>

So what we see from the Moving Average study is an expected second expansion. So I placed my order after the breakout not on the 4th but the 5th. I then saw easy expansion but some reversal. Why didn't I quit the position out of fear, even though I hadn't yet done today's study (the new green fibonacci fan)? It was because the drawback happened inside the rapid expansion bubble, meaning "Bull flag". However, we're not out of the woods yet. So I ran the fan study, and sure enough we saw some steep upward pressure. The question then remains: how long will this go?

The thing is, we do not know how the Justin "communist" Trudeau reaction and seizure of crypto market will affect it, nor how the entire market will react to what is turning out to be a Black Swan event the NWO probably did not intend when they began squeezing the logistics supply chain with politically leveraged lockdowns and fascism. However, will they capitalize on it? Or will it harm their leveraged positions? We don't have any data as to how toxic and exposed they are in the derivatives market. Most of these private funds are just that: private. If they have cross collateralized credit default swaps, it may be a buffer, or gasoline on the fire, as they say. We don't have any data.

So we resort back to the fundamental analysis, with some technicals. Jobs markets are a poor indicator because it is a lagging measure instead of a forward measure like the above Moving Average study.

Whatever we see, we see a continuation of expansion should last, with uplifting pressure throughout the rest of the spiral til the crossing on March 2nd! That's a time hopefully we do not "burn" through all the fan support. If we do then the world economy is worse off than we thought, and they are drawing out of the crypto market (hedge) to cover losses. I'd expect the housing market to crash, if that is the case. First thing right off the bat.

As for fuel and commodities, that all depends on velocities, and it isn't the purview of this study series to follow that. But a secondary study overlaying the prices and comparing the S&P, commodities, FOREX, and Bitcoin should be undertaken to look for "data leylines" connecting various markets together, forming a non linear mathematical circuit structure (vortitional?).

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In figure 3 we see consolidation around the fan, and the Bollinger Bands slowing in “volumocity”. This may be a caterpillar effect (compression wave), or a deceleration. It will be clear within 2 days.

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga